

Deliverable 4.3: Scientific Workshop- Oncology

World Cancer Day and Cancer Research Day

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Basic information

Project title	Strategies to strengthen scientific excellence and innovation capacity for early diagnosis of gastrointestinal cancers
Project acronym	VISION
Call	H2020-WIDESPREAD-2018-2020
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Grant Agreement No.	857381
Nature	R
Dissemination level	PU

Executive summary

The Scientific Workshop – Oncology (SWO) is a project of the Cancer Research Institute, BMC SAV, and the Slovak Cancer Research Foundation (SCRF). The time allotted for this activity is determined by February 4 (World Cancer Day) and March 7 (Cancer Research Day). The main objective of the SWO is to direct young people's attention to cancer research to recruit gifted secondary students to study at the Faculties of Medical or Natural Sciences, creating a pool of future graduates at universities interested in the Ph.D. study in the field of Oncology and Genetics. In addition, SWO is aimed to promote oncological research and points at the necessity of cancer prevention from primary (avoiding harmful environmental factors and adopting a healthy lifestyle) to tertiary (management of the unwanted side effects of treatment). Moreover, SWO motivates high school students to work as a volunteer in laboratories and get involved in the nationwide competition "Secondary School Professional Activities".

1 Description of work & main achievements

Ph.D. students and senior scientists visit secondary schools all over Slovakia. During secondary school visits, Ph.D. students present the research projects they are working on to the students in an understandable way. In addition, senior scientists give more general talks aimed at elucidating the causes of cancer, diagnostic options, and new approaches to treating malignant tumors based on the latest discoveries while minimizing damage to healthy cells. The presentation also includes information on the activities of the SCRF. The lectures are followed by an informal discussion, during which students can ask early-stage researchers or senior scientists about things that interest them. Such interaction is very popular among students and their teachers.

1.1 Scientific workshop – Oncology in 2020

1.1.1 World Cancer Day 2020

World Cancer Day (WCD) is the global uniting initiative led by the Union for International Cancer Control (UICC). On the occasion of WCD (February 4, 2020), the SCRF, in close cooperation with the Cancer Research Institute, BMC SAV, organized a conference, "Integrative Oncology 2". Before the start, the conference participants commemorated this event with the slogan "I Am and I Will" and posted a personal message to the WCD participants worldwide.

The slogan of World Cancer Day 2020

Participants of the conference supported this event by gathering in front of the conference hall.

Registration to the conference

Main organizers of the conference

Participants of the conference

More information about the conference is available at <https://www.nvr.sk/konferencia-pri-prilezitosti-svetoveho-dna-proti-rakovine-2020/> (in Slovak).

1.1.2 Scientific Workshop - Oncology in 2020

This year visited Ph.D. students and senior scientists in a total of thirty-seven secondary schools, including one school in Ukraine, and presented 112 lectures.

Overview of secondary schools in Slovakia that participated in the SWO project.

Students of the secondary schools listening to the lectures

The complete list of visited schools is available at <https://www.nvr.sk/akcie/galakonzert-ku-dnu-vyskumu-rakoviny-2020/>

1.2 Scientific workshop – Oncology in 2021

Due to the bad epidemiological situation (COVID-19 pandemic) and strict travel restrictions, the SWO was canceled.

1.3 Scientific workshop – Oncology in 2022

Due to the ongoing unfavourable epidemiological situation, all activities realized in 2022 were held online.

1.3.1 World Cancer Day 2022

In 2022, the global cancer community commemorated WCD with the slogan "Close the care gap." On the occasion of WCD, on February 4, 2022, the SCRF, in close cooperation with the Cancer Research Institute, BMC SAV, organized an online workshop entitled: "Peripheral neuropathy caused by chemotherapy." The speakers provided basic information about the nervous system, the causes of its damage/dysfunction, and the current and potential options shortly to minimize the problem of peripheral neuropathy caused by chemotherapy. The list of lectures and more information about this event is available at: <https://www.nvr.sk/akcie/2022-world-cancer-day/> (in Slovak).

1.3.2 Scientific Workshop - Oncology in 2022

This year, instead of visits to secondary schools, the presentations of Ph.D. students and young scientists were recorded and made available to secondary schools in advance. Later, in agreement with the teachers, online discussions were held, where the lecturers answered the pupils' questions. The short video began with a brief introduction of the Ph.D. student and the laboratory where she/he performed the experiments. Then the presentation continued with introducing the Ph.D. thesis and its aims.

A novelty of this year's SWO was the inclusion of lectures by psychologists from the Institute of Clinical Psychology from the Faculty of Psychology at the Pan European University. Ph.D. students and psychologists gave 83 individual lectures, and 21 secondary schools from different regions of Slovakia registered and participated in this event.

Lenka Trnková, MSc., a Ph.D. student, completed an academic stay within the VISION project in Spain in 2021 and in Norway in 2022

Lucia Balintová, MSc., a Ph.D. student, completed an academic stay within the VISION project in Spain in 2022. Her co-supervisor is Dr. rer. nat. Yvonne Kohl - Fraunhofer-Institut für Biomedizinische Technik IBMT, Sulzbach, Germany (FhG)

Verona Buciková, MSc., a Ph.D. student. Her co-supervisor is assoc. Prof. Mária Dušinská, DSc. - Norwegian Institute for Air Research, Oslo, Norway (NILU)

Michaela Blažičková, MSc., a Ph.D. student. Her co-supervisor is assoc. Prof. Mária Dušinská, DSc. - Norwegian Institute for Air Research, Oslo, Norway (NILU)

Kristína Jakič, MSc., a Ph.D. student, completed an academic stay within the VISION project in 2022 in Germany. Her co-supervisor is Dr. rer. nat. Yvonne Kohl - Fraunhofer-Institut für Biomedizinische Technik IBMT, Sulzbach, Germany (FhG)

Mária Urbanová, MSc., a Ph.D. student, completed an academic stay within the VISION project in Spain in 2021 and in Norway in 2022. Her co-supervisor is Julie Earl, PhD. - Instituto Ramón y Cajal de Investigación Sanitaria, Madrid, Spain (IRYCIS)

The list of secondary schools and speakers is available at: <https://www.nvr.sk/akcie/vedecke-dielne-onkologia-2022/> (in Slovak).

1.3.3 Young Oncologist Award 2022

The Young Oncologist Workshop/Award competition was held online on March 7 – 8, 2022, in 3 categories, 1. Undergraduate students, 2. Ph.D. students, and 3. Post-docs up to 35 years. This year, undergraduate and Ph.D. students and post-docs from consortium partners also participated in this event. More information about this event is available in the deliverable D4.5.

1.3.4 `Secondary School Professional Activities' Award 2022

The positive impact of the SWO event was demonstrated in students' increased interest in secondary school professional activities and their motivation to work as volunteers in the laboratories under the supervision of Ph.D. students. One of them, Štefan Hlušák, a student at the Ladislav Novomeský Grammar School in Bratislava, was awarded the 1st prize at the regional round of the `Secondary School Professional Activities' (Stredoškolská odborná činnosť, SOČ) competition and the 2nd prize at the nationwide round of SOČ competition in the

field of "Biology." He prepared his student work entitled: 'Cytotoxic and genotoxic effects of 5-fluorouracil on HT-29 colorectal carcinoma cells' at the Department of Nanobiology, BMC SAV, under the supervision of Alena Gábelová, Ph.D. and the guidance of Lucia Bálintová, MSc., a Ph.D. student.

Štefan Hlušák

The 1st prize at the regional round of the 'Secondary School Professional Activities' competition

The 2nd prize at the nationwide round of the 'Secondary School Professional Activities' competition

Currently, a secondary school student, Martin Rak, works at the Department of Nanobiology, BMC SAV, as a volunteer. He plans to participate in 'Secondary School Professional Activities' competitions and also Young Oncologist Award in 2024 in the secondary school category.

1.4 Scientific workshop – Oncology in 2023

1.4.1 World Cancer day 2023

In 2023, the SCRF, in close cooperation with the Cancer Research Institute, BMC SAV, organized at the Bojnice castle a 'round-table discussion' of experts entitled "Close the Care Gap" in a hybrid event mode. Despite the progress in cancer research, the experts discussed the regional disparities in cancer prevention, diagnosis, and treatment availability. More information about this event is available at <https://www.nvr.sk/akcie/2023-world-cancer-day/> (in Slovak)

Invitation to 'round-table discussion.'

1.4.2 Cancer Research Day – March 7, 2023

On the occasion of Cancer Research Day, a conference entitled: "A continuum of patient-focused scientific research" was held. The organizer of this event was SCRF and the National Oncology Institute, partners in the ECHoS (Establishing of Cancer Mission Hubs: Networks and Synergies) projects. Representatives of various scientific and research institutions in Slovakia presented the actual topics in cancer research they are working on, informed about the education for Ph.D. students and medical personnel, about the creation of a central biobank, about the state of cancer screening in Slovakia, and presented the possibilities of active participation in the EU Cancer Mission.

Cancer Research Day logo

Invitation to "A continuum of patient-focused scientific research" conference.

Prof. Silvia Pastoreková, DSc., the general director of BMC SAV, also presented the VISION project's main objectives at this event.

ZÁKLADNÝ A TRANSLAČNÝ ONKOLOGICKÝ VÝSKUM V BMC SAV, v. v. i.

VISION
STRATEGIES TO STRENGTHEN SCIENTIFIC EXCELLENCE AND INNOVATION CAPACITY FOR EARLY DIAGNOSIS OF GASTROINTESTINAL CANCERS

Slovensko patrí ku krajinám s najvyšším výskytom zhubných nádorov tráviaceho traktu v Európe (najmä karcinóm kolorekta a pankreasu). Spolupráca s významnými vedeckými inštitúciami prispieje ku zvýšeniu kvality výskumu, prenosu vedeckých výsledkov do klinickej praxe a zlepšeniu úrovne odborného vzdelávania.

CIELE
Vedecká excelentnosť
Nové možnosti onkologického výskumu
Profesionálny rozvoj začínajúcich výskumných pracovníkov a lekárov
Kvalitné vzdelávanie
Zvýšené povedomie verejnosti o nutnosti prevencie

NÁSTROJE
Špecializované kurzy, akademické pobyty, semináre, pozvané prednášky, letná škola pre študentov, konferencie, spolupráca pri vzdelávaní doktorandov, aktivity pre laickú verejnosť

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SLOVAKIA: BIOCENTRUM SLOVENSKEJ AKADEMIE VIED
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VIAC VÍDEI

SCAN ME

<http://vision.sav.sk/trainings.html>

More information about this event is available at <https://www.nvr.sk/akcie/4079/> (in Slovak).

1.4.3 Scientific Workshop - Oncology in 2023

Due to unexpected objective reasons, the Scientific Workshop - Oncology education event did not take place this year.

2 Deviation from the workplan

The event Scientific Workshop - Oncology took place according to the schedule updated in the amendment to the Grant Agreement of the VISION project. Only in 2021, when teaching at secondary schools was carried out exclusively only by online form, this educational event did not take place.

3 Conclusion

The Scientific Workshop – Oncology is an occasion for secondary school students to get up-to-date information about oncological research and motivate them to select biology and medicine as a topic for their further professional development. The SWO action is bordered by two important events - World Cancer Day (February 4) and Cancer Research Day (March 7). Teachers, as well as students at secondary schools, highly credit the SWO activity. As a result, the interest in participating in scientific competitions (Secondary School Professional Activities and Young Oncologist Award) is increasing.